

Locative Audio Technology for Exploring Green Stormwater Infrastructure: A Preliminary Study

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Abstract. Locative audio is an emerging technology in mobile cartography to create immersive and accessible user experiences. This work-in-progress advances a mobile application (app) designed to guide users through green stormwater infrastructure projects in Shorewood, Wisconsin. The app uses locative audio to educate the public about green stormwater infrastructure's role in mitigating urban flooding and runoff pollution. This submission integrates findings from a comparative analysis of existing apps and expert feedback to highlight locative audio's potential in geospatial technology. By sharing these advancements, we aim to contribute to discussions on locative audio's role in inclusive and interactive learning experiences.

Keywords. Locative audio, user-centered design, mobile cartography, green infrastructure, location-based services

1. Introduction

This study investigates locative audio design and technology within mobile cartography, aiming to explore its potential applications, challenges, and implications for user experiences. *Locative audio* refers to the strategic placement of sound within the landscape (Behrendt 2015) and it is now widely supported through mobile device's GPS and spatial sensors to deliver sounds as users move (Indans, Hauthal, and Burghardt 2019). Mobile guided tours are a common example of this, where audio leads the users through a series of points of interest while providing information on the historical, geographical, and otherwise invisible dimensions of these places (Roth et al. 2018).

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Despite its growing relevance to both mobile-first and inclusive design, *sound cartography* remains underexplored in cartographic research compared to visual approaches (Schiewe 2014). Research on locative audio is particularly crucial for inclusive design since audio and multimodal interaction can enhance safety by reducing visual overload and promote accessibility for non-sighted users (D'Ignazio and Klein 2016).

In this work-in-progress, we attempt to develop a locative audio mobile app offering users a guided tour of recent and planned green stormwater infrastructure projects in the Village of Shorewood in Wisconsin, USA. Shorewood has adopted several practices to effectively manage stormwater issues such as flooding and runoff pollution. Therefore, this tour can serve as an educational tool for the audience to learn about these practices and their impact on society.

2. Methodology

2.1. Comparative Analysis

As part of our background study, we analyzed top-ranked mobile apps, expanding the sample through web and app store searches, to assess existing technologies. We selected 38 apps that were fully functional, included audio, used an interactive map, and suggested at least one tour route. We analyzed these tours by five criteria: app technologies, tour characteristics, visual representations, sonic representations, and interactions to understand the state-of-the-art in locative audio platforms. (Roth et al., 2023)

2.2. Prototyping and Testing

The results of the comparative analysis informed the design of our prototypes. We identified VoiceMap¹ and Echoes² from the analysis as two candidate platforms given their overall utility and stability. We also developed a third prototype using Leaflet.js³ which is an open-source JavaScript library for mobile-friendly interactive maps. We tested these three alternatives with seven experts on our case study walking tour of green stormwater infrastructure in Shorewood. The walk was followed by a survey and focus group discussion to collect feedback on the five

¹ <https://voicemap.me/>

² <https://echoes.xyz/>

³ Initial Prototype - <https://uwcartlab.github.io/mke-audio-tour/>

aforementioned criteria. The evaluations revealed issues like unsafe crossings, route confusion, audio playback issues, discrepancies between audio length and walking distance, and the need for more engaging storytelling content.

3. Refinements

We refined the route design and story content based on the insights gained from the comparative analysis and field evaluation as well as follow-up meetings with local stakeholders in Shorewood. *Figure 1* illustrates these changes. The following updates were made to enhance the app and its educational goals:

- **Technology Choice:** We selected Leaflet.js⁴ as the primary technology for its open-source nature, flexibility, and cross-platform compatibility allowing us to adapt the app as necessary.
- **Route Redesign:** We shortened the route from 3 miles to approximately 2.25 miles (4.8 kilometers to 3.6 kilometers) and adopted a looping design for easier navigation. We increased the number of stops from 8 to 10, each featuring a unique green stormwater infrastructure, with additional audio content provided between stops. We also incorporated accessible path information and alternate routes to accommodate diverse users.
- **Geofencing and Timing:** We adjusted the geofencing radius to ensure seamless audio playback. Audio duration was expanded from 4 minutes to an extensive 90 minutes, incorporating additional context and directional guidance, aligning content with typical walking speed and ensuring synchronized content delivery.
- **Narrative Enhancement:** We restructured the entire script with clear educational objectives, fostering user engagement and deeper connection to the environmental and societal impacts of green stormwater infrastructure.
- **Audio Integration:** We incorporated directional audio cues and safety alerts to improve navigation and promote personal safety. To enhance immersion, we layered ambient sounds beneath the narration to support context-specific storytelling. For example, during a segment that explains what happens during a rainfall

⁴ Refined Prototype - <https://ntnawshin.github.io/Shorewood-Walking-Tour/>

event, we used the sound of distant thunder followed by rain to evoke the sensory experience of a storm.

- **Interactive Elements:** We integrated real-time photos, custom diagrams, maps, and critical thinking prompts at each stop to enhance the narrative, reinforce learning outcomes, and sustain user engagement.
- **Design and Functionality Updates:** We improved overall app usability and accessibility by prioritizing features like user-friendly navigation, dark mode for improved visibility, responsive design, and cross-device compatibility.

Figure 1. The app interface before (left) and aer (right) the design refinements.

4. Future Directions

Our future plans involve broader user evaluations in the Spring of 2025 to refine the app further. These evaluations will inform the final app design, contributing to its integration into educational and community outreach programs.

5. Conclusion

This study presents early efforts to integrate locative audio into a mobile guided tour for green stormwater infrastructure. Updates made based on comparative analysis and expert feedback have strengthened the educational content, navigational clarity, and inclusive design aspects of the prototype. While the design is still undergoing iterations, these refinements establish a foundation for broader user evaluations planned for Summer 2025. As an initial phase of a larger study, this work aims to advance the design and understanding of accessible, audio-based mobile cartography. By integrating geofenced audio and spatially anchored storytelling, this project demonstrates how locative audio can expand the design space of location-based services for public education and place-based engagement.

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